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JOINUS4HEALTH: THREE COHORTS (SHIP, ROTTERDAM STUDY AND BIALYSTOK PLUS) AND THEIR PATHWAY TO RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION VIA CROWD-SOURCING

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Introduction

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) may offer opportunities to counteract declining response in cohort research, which has been observed worldwide for years. RRI involves engagement of multiple societal groups in research and easier access to science results and education. More targeted and wider communication of cohort findings in easy-to-understand language may also raise awareness and perceived value of cohort studies in local communities. We aim to a) present a roadmap to combine RRI and crowdsourcing as converging approaches to promote inclusive innovation and citizen engagement and b) to assess effects on response in cohort research.

Methods

Three population-based cohort studies (SHIP, Germany; Rotterdam Study, Netherlands; Bialystok PLUS, Poland) have generated up to 31 follow-up years of health data for 27,000 participants to date. As part of the EU H2020 funded JoinUs4Health project (01/21-12/23), these cohorts strive to create knowledge in closer proximity to society and stimulate interactive forms of knowledge production. 'Citizen science boards' and 'Monitoring and Evaluation groups' are engaged in design and revision of activities and procedures (in total 60 representatives from five groups - citizens, science, policy, business, education).

Results

We present a RRI roadmap combining several pathways to generate RRI by means of crowdsourcing. The presentation includes an outline of the underlying concept, b) web-platform (full release: 12/2021), c) communication and dissemination strategy, d) engagement approaches, e) institutional changes and f) evaluation strategies (response, attitude towards science).

Conclusions/Outlook

By engaging cohort participants, citizens and other groups of societal actors in a more co-creative manner, population-based research may become more sensitive to societal expectations and concerns and enhance citizens' preparedness to participate in cohort research.